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A review of annual statements on research integrity from UK institutions in 2023-4, with a focus on research fraud

Dorothy V. M. Bishop
Department of Experimental Psychology
University of Oxford
OX2 6GG

dorothy.bishop@psy.ox.ac.uk

17

18 Abstract

19 **Background.** Estimates of the frequency of research misconduct appear much higher
20 in self-report surveys than would be expected from numbers of institutional
21 investigations, but there is little hard data on this topic.

22 **Method.** UK universities produce annual statements on research integrity. The most
23 recent statements were analysed and compared with evidence of
24 fabrication/falsification of data from reports on the PubPeer website.

25 **Results.** In 117 institutional statements with useable data, there were only 25
26 allegations of fabrication or falsification involving 13 universities. On PubPeer
27 comments in 2023 for all publications that included a lead UK author there were 49
28 comments describing fabrication/falsification of data (mostly digitally manipulated
29 images), and 28 with hallmarks of a paper mill. Only nine universities had more than
30 one PubPeer entry compatible with fabrication/falsification, but four of these involved
31 senior researchers with multiple problematic publications; in none of these cases had
32 the institution upheld an allegation of misconduct.

33 **Conclusions.** It is recommended that it should not be left to the employing institution
34 to deal with allegations of serious research misconduct, that PubPeer could be used
35 proactively in investigations of misconduct, and that research integrity reports should
36 be made openly available to increase confidence in the process.

37

38 **Keywords:** fabrication, falsification, institutional investigation, research integrity
39 officer, PubPeer, transparency

40 1. Introduction

41 In a report on a recent Delphi survey, Bishop (2025) noted that there was strong
42 polarisation of views about frequency of serious research misconduct, and adequacy
43 of processes for investigating it. The definition of serious research misconduct
44 encompassed fraud (i.e., fabrication, falsification, plagiarism), and reckless or
45 negligent behaviour with the potential to cause harm. In general, research integrity
46 officers judged that serious research misconduct was not common and current
47 processes for handling allegations, while not perfect, worked reasonably well. In
48 contrast, individuals who undertake independent investigations of research fraud and
49 related issues (often referred to as research "sleuths") regarded rates of serious
50 research misconduct to be high enough to pose a serious threat to science, and
51 concluded that formal processes for investigating and responding to this issue were
52 generally unfit for purpose. Since those who engage in research fraud and related
53 misconduct attempt to hide their activities, this topic is hard to investigate. The current
54 article first considers existing evidence for these opposing perspectives, before
55 presenting new empirical data from institutional statements on research integrity from
56 UK institutions, and from PubPeer comments for the same institutions.

57 1.1. Evidence of research misconduct from surveys

58 The main source of evidence about rates of research misconduct comes from studies
59 where researchers are asked about their experience of various forms of misconduct.
60 Surveys typically ask respondents to rate how commonly they observe misconduct in
61 colleagues, as well as to give estimates of their own behaviour, because the latter is
62 likely to be an underestimate. The most widely-cited source of evidence of this kind
63 comes from a meta-analysis of survey data by Fanelli (2009), which reported "*A pooled
64 weighted average of 1.97% (N=7, 95%CI: 0.86–4.45) of scientists admitted to have
65 fabricated, falsified or modified data or results at least once In surveys asking
66 about the behaviour of colleagues, admission rates were 14.12% (N=12, 95% CI: 9.91–
67 19.72) for falsification.*" Fanelli noted that, given the sensitive nature of the topic, these
68 estimates are likely to be conservative. In a recent preprint, Heathers (2024, not peer-
69 reviewed) attempted to synthesize literature on this topic, and came to a similar
70 conclusion: approximately 1 in 7 scientific papers are either intentionally fabricated or
71 intentionally falsified. However, he also pointed out that the literature is so variable that
72 it does not allow for meta-analysis. Another source is a UK-based study by Williams
73 and Roberts (2020, not peer-reviewed) that used both qualitative (focus group) and
74 quantitative (survey) methods. The survey had 329 responses from research-active
75 academics, and found that around one in five of them reported having fabricated
76 research data. Reports of falsification were much less common.

77
78 Fanelli's review predated the boom in paper mills, commercial outfits that sell
79 authorship of publications for profit. Van Noorden (2023) estimated that 1.5% to 2% of
80 all scientific papers published in 2022 resemble paper-mill works, with biology and
81 medicine being the most affected. Many paper mill products are plagiarised or
82 fabricated. It is not clear how much impact paper mills have on UK universities; most
83 paper mill authors are based outside of Europe and the USA (Parker et al., 2024).

84 1.2. Evidence of research misconduct from RetractionWatch

85 The Retraction Watch Database is a freely available database which documents all
86 articles that have been retracted. For their Annual Statement of 2024, the UK
87 Committee on Research Integrity (UKCORI) conducted an analysis of all papers in the
88 database with a UK-based author (UKCORI, 2024). The results appeared reassuring: in
89 the UK, retraction rates were below 0.05% of all published papers, and comparable to
90 that for other countries in the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and
91 Development. There were 407 articles that were published since 2017 and retracted
92 within two years of publication. Reasons for retraction were "concerns/issues about
93 data" (71 cases), "unreliable results" (54 cases), and "concerns/issues about results".
94 A relatively small number of retractions seems related to paper mill fraud (Abalkina et
95 al., 2025), as evidenced by reasons such as "fake peer review" or "randomly generated
96 content", though it was noted that this may be more of a problem in future. Finally, the
97 UKCORI report noted that retractions do not give definitive evidence of misconduct:
98 authors may ask for their article to be retracted if they find errors in the data or analysis
99 - a sign of research integrity - and some retractions are due to publisher error.

100

101 Overall, the analysis of retractions suggested that there is a very low rate of (detected)
102 research misconduct by UK researchers, but there is a serious limitation to this
103 evidence: it can take years for an article to be retracted even when blatant evidence of
104 falsification or fabrication is pointed out to a publisher, and many fraudulent articles
105 remain unretracted (Bik, 2024; Grey et al., 2020; Oransky, 2022).

106 1.3. Evidence of research misconduct from institutional statements

107 A further source of evidence that may help throw light on the reasons for polarised
108 views is a set of annual statements that UK universities are required to produce to be
109 compliant with the UK's Concordat to Support Research Integrity (UK Committee on
110 Research Integrity, 2025). As noted by Chiarelli et al. (2023) in their report on these
111 statements (commissioned by UKCORI and the Research Integrity Concordat Signatory
112 group): *"The data included in these statements has been undervalued and
113 underutilised. There has been limited analysis of these statements in the past few
114 years, but a thorough and full review of the data within them is expected to offer a more
115 complete understanding of research integrity across the system, provide a baseline
116 from which trends can be monitored and highlight areas where the greatest attention is
117 required."* However, insights from the report are limited because the underlying dataset
118 has been edited to redact quantitative information about misconduct allegations and to
119 anonymise identity of institutions. The authors give the rationale for this approach:
120 *"Throughout this report, and in the supporting data released via Zenodo, we do not
121 name these institutions, except for cases where they are used as part of a good practice
122 case study. This is to avoid the metricisation of our findings, which are meant to paint a
123 picture of research integrity across the UK and not as a means for ranking or
124 comparison."* Furthermore, the focus is on *"narrative discussion rather than
125 quantification, so as to avoid incorrect or inappropriate generalisations that may not
126 reflect the diversity of institutions considered"*.

127 Data from the Chiarelli et al. report will be presented in more detail below; in general
128 they support the notion that allegations of research misconduct are rare in UK
129 institutions, and when such allegations occur, they are frequently not upheld. Thus, as
130 with the data from Retraction Watch, estimates of research misconduct from
131 institutional annual statements are considerably lower than estimates obtained by
132 surveys of researchers.

133 1.4. Evidence of research misconduct from post-publication peer review

134 Post-publication peer review can provide evidence of potential research misconduct
135 affecting peer-reviewed publications in journals. This will exclude much of the
136 humanities, where books and monographs are a more common form of research
137 output, as well as problematic content in research theses.

138 PubPeer is a site where anyone can write a review of a published paper, so long as it
139 provides factual support for any statements and does not contain any personal
140 comments about authors. The requirement is that comments contain "facts, logic and
141 verifiable information". Those who report on PubPeer may choose to be anonymous, in
142 which case they are given a botanical name. If their email address is available, authors
143 are informed of comments and encouraged to reply. Although PubPeer was initially set
144 up as a journal club, and comments may be positive or trivial, the majority are critical,
145 and the site has been used to expose major problems in the work of some researchers.
146 It is sometimes portrayed as a site where malicious allegations are made about
147 researchers, but the moderation policy makes it difficult for bad actors to have a
148 presence (PubPeer, 2024). Comments tend to cluster on certain authors because if a
149 research sleuth discovers an anomaly, they are likely to focus attention on other work
150 by the same author; a single error in an article can always be the result of honest error,
151 but a pattern of errors over a body of work is a strong indication of misconduct.
152 Nevertheless, PubPeer has been criticised as creating a "conundrum" for research
153 integrity investigations, by overwhelming institutions who "*cannot spend every waking*
154 *hour reviewing PubPeer comments and other potential concerns of research*
155 *misconduct originating on blogs, social media, and other online sources.*" (Caron, Lye,
156 Bierer, & Barnes, 2024, p. 16).

157 Another source of evidence is the *For Better Science* website run by Leonid Schneider,
158 which started in 2015 and is now a substantial public record of criticisms of
159 researchers and research studies (Schneider, undated). Although Schneider
160 meticulously documents evidence of research fraud from PubPeer, he goes beyond
161 objective descriptions of errors in research to make accusations of misconduct against
162 researchers, typically drawing on a whole series of publications rather than individual
163 papers, and he includes mockery and personal abuse about researchers while
164 describing suspicious findings in their research. This aspect of the website may explain
165 why many institutions adopt antagonistic or dismissive attitudes to *For Better Science*,
166 even though it has been an important source for documenting some high-profile cases
167 of fraud.

168
169 The informal impression from PubPeer and *For Better Science* is that serious research
170 misconduct, in the form of fabrication and falsification of data, is common in science,

171 as is implied in the self-report surveys summarised above. However, it remains unclear
172 how far this perception is due to a small number of researchers who engage in repeated
173 misconduct, or whether it is more widespread. By its very nature, serious research
174 misconduct is usually hidden, making it hard to establish rates of occurrence. In
175 addition, it is unclear how many findings suggestive of serious research misconduct
176 implicate researchers from UK institutions.

177 2. Aims of the current study

178 The primary aim of the current study is to review the latest annual statements of
179 research integrity from UK institutions, as was done for earlier years in the 2023 report
180 commissioned by UKCORI (Chiarelli et al., 2023). Research Consulting has been
181 commissioned to do an updated report covering 2023-2024, but this has not yet been
182 published. It seems likely that this will adopt the same approach as the previous report,
183 and so lack transparency about the identity of institutions and not report quantitative
184 data.

185
186 By producing a report that includes these variables, the goal is to gain insight into the
187 gulf in perceptions of rates of fraudulent research between research integrity officers
188 and sleuths. The focus was just on the most recent academic year of reporting for
189 which a statement could be found online, typically 2022-2023 or 2023-2024.

190
191 To complement this analysis, data from the annual statements were considered in the
192 context of comments on PubPeer for authors from the same institutions, with a
193 particular focus on comments that suggest there has been fraud, i.e., plagiarism,
194 fabrication or falsification of data. For cases where the same research group had
195 several comments suggestive of research fraud, the *For Better Science* website was
196 checked for coverage.

197 3. Methods

198 3.1. Quantitative data from annual statements

199 As a first step, a list of member institutions of [Universities UK](#) was compiled and a web
200 search conducted for the most recent annual statement of research integrity. As noted
201 by Chiarelli et al. (2023), there is no central site for these reports, and so a manual
202 Google search was conducted between 12 April and 22 April 2025. A search term that
203 combined the name of the institution with the words "research integrity annual" was
204 usually adequate for locating a statement, though if this was ineffective, the institution
205 name with "research integrity" generally led to a site that might provide a link to annual
206 statements. The search was run again on August 18th 2025 and a further 10 reports
207 were discovered, leaving 14 institutions with no statement. It seems unlikely that any
208 reports were missed. In seven of these cases, there was a website with statements of
209 research integrity, but these had not been updated beyond 2022. In the remaining
210 cases, the institutional website contained only sparse information about research
211 integrity: these were all teaching-focused institutions.

212

213 The reports used in this analysis were saved in *pdf* format and are available in
 214 *Supplement 1*. These reports contain variable amounts of narrative text describing the
 215 research integrity procedures adopted by the institution, and topics such as lessons
 216 learned from previous experience.

217
 218 For quantitative data, most reports used a standard template grid developed by the UK
 219 Research Integrity Office (UKRIO, 2022), as shown in Table 1, for reporting numbers of
 220 allegations of research misconduct and their outcomes.

221

222 *Table 1: UKRIO template for reporting allegations of research misconduct*

Type of allegation	Number of allegations reported to the organisation	Number of formal investigations	Number upheld in part after formal investigation	Number upheld in full after formal investigation
Fabrication				
Falsification				
Plagiarism				
Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations				
Misrepresentation (eg data involvement; interests; qualification; and/or publication history)				
Improper dealing with allegations of misconduct				
Multiple areas of concern (when received in a single allegation)				
Other				
Total				

223
 224 Instructions for completion are as follows:
 225 *"Please complete the table on the number of formal investigations completed during*
 226 *the period under review (including investigations which completed during this period*
 227 *but started in a previous academic year). Information from ongoing investigations*
 228 *should not be submitted.*

229 *An organisation's procedure may include an initial, preliminary, or screening stage to*
230 *determine whether a formal investigation needs to be completed. These allegations*
231 *should be included in the first column but only those that proceeded past this stage, to*
232 *formal investigations, should be included in the second column."*

233

234 When transferring numbers from reports using this format, the surrounding text was
235 scrutinised and notes added to provide context where possible.

236

237 UK institutions cover a massive range in terms of size and research activity. To get a
238 rough indicator of both characteristics, two additional variables were estimated: (a)
239 Size of institution. This was based on online data on number of students reported for
240 2023-4 (Table 1) by the Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA, undated) and (b)
241 Number of research outputs. The latter was obtained by searching the [Dimensions](#)
242 database for research outputs where the Country/Territory of the Research
243 Organisation was United Kingdom for the date range 2023 to 2024.

244 The database of coded Annual Statements used in the current analysis is available as
245 *Supplementary Material 2*.

246 **3.2. PubPeer listings for 2023.**

247 These were provided by PubPeer for articles published in 2023 where any author had an
248 address in the UK. Records were coded for the following variables.

249 **The identity of the institution**

250 If more than one UK institution was included, the institution of the first or last authors
251 was used, or, if neither first or last author was from the UK, the first UK institution in the
252 author list was used.

253 **Institutional contribution**

254 Given that many papers involve authors from several countries/institutions, a measure
255 was devised to reflect the institutional involvement in an article. Each publication was
256 assigned to a single institution, with no double-counting. For the current analysis, the
257 focus is just on articles where the first, last or corresponding author was from a UK
258 institution. If more than one UK institution was represented, then the publication was
259 attributed to that of the corresponding author.

260 **Categorisation of comments in relation to evidence of research** 261 **misconduct**

262 PubPeer is intended as a platform to report comments about publications, not to report
263 misconduct, and comments alluding to authors' motivations or wrongdoing are
264 moderated out. Nevertheless, the content of comments can indicate problems with
265 published papers that appear to go beyond academic debate, detection of suboptimal
266 methods or honest error.

267 Accordingly, comments were scrutinised and categorised according to an ad hoc
268 system devised to capture the range of content, with a particular focus on
269 distinguishing between comments suggestive of misconduct and the remainder. I
270 started with a rough taxonomy of codes based on personal experience, which was then
271 refined as it was applied to the corpus of comments. There was inevitably a subjective
272 element to this coding, but all records and codes are openly available so that readers
273 can check how justified individual codes are (see *Supplementary Material 3*).

274 **Comments not indicative of misconduct**

275 1. Minor errors, such as mislabelling.

276 2. Detailed review of methods or logic. Some commentators engaged in detailed post-
277 publication peer review of the kind that was originally envisaged for the PubPeer
278 platform. Although these were often critical, this could be seen as robust scientific
279 debate which did not imply misconduct. Where it was difficult to judge without subject-
280 specific expertise, it was assumed that comments on methodological aspects were of
281 this type. Some authors engaged positively with commentators.

282 3. A serious problem with data that could plausibly reflect honest error where the
283 authors engage to explain this and/or correct it. Errors could reflect duplication of an
284 image within a paper to illustrate groups or conditions that should be different,
285 impossible or implausible data values, or a wrongly reported genetic sequence. In
286 general, this code was used when it was judged that a reputable researcher would not
287 ignore a problem that was this serious.

288 **Comments that could indicate misconduct**

289 4. Serious errors in the data similar to those noted under (3) where the authors fail to
290 give a satisfactory explanation, or obfuscate and/or attack the commentator. Where
291 there was uncertainty about the sufficiency of an author's response, they were given
292 the benefit of the doubt, so code 4 was used only if the author ignored a serious
293 problem or attempted to cover it up. In general, corresponding authors are notified
294 when a PubPeer comment appears, and given the opportunity to respond; however, if
295 the PubPeer record did not show an associated author email, code 3 was used, as it
296 could not be assumed the author was aware of the comment.

297 5. Undocumented departure from protocol in a registered study.

298 6. Failure to report ethics approval for a study that requires it.

299 7. Undeclared conflict of interest.

300 8. Authorship/affiliation issues. This included guest authorship, or misleading affiliation
301 or email. This code excluded articles with the hallmarks of a paper mill (see below).

302 **Comments strongly suggestive of research fraud**

303 9. Evidence of plagiarism or self-plagiarism

304 10. Evidence that the article comes from a paper mill. Paper mill outputs typically
305 involve elements of fabrication or falsification but were categorised separately here,
306 because they have the distinctive feature that researchers have purchased authorship.
307 They can also be identified by other characteristics, including evidence from the
308 Problematic Paper Screener (Cabanac, Labbé, & Magazinov, 2022), which notes
309 "tortured phrases", citation of retracted, questionable or otherwise unreliable sources,
310 and indicators of compromised editorial or peer review processes. Another indicator is
311 numerous co-authors from many different countries in a context where this is hard to
312 explain, or a co-author with a strong track record of paper mill publications. In general,
313 there is no one definitive indicator of paper mill products. This code would not be
314 applied if there was just a single instance of a tortured phrase or inappropriate citation
315 in an article; rather the judgement is made from the presence of more than one "red
316 flag" such as these. Finally, some paper mill products can be identified from a
317 retraction notice; the publisher Hindawi retracted thousands of papers after its journals
318 became infested with paper mill products (Bik, 2023).

319 11. Evidence of data fabrication or falsification. Fabrication (making up data) and
320 falsification (altering existing data) can be hard to distinguish and so are treated
321 together here. Some PubPeer comments included screenshots that show
322 manipulations of data that are difficult to explain other than as a deliberate attempt to
323 mislead. The main category here is digital manipulation of images. This goes beyond
324 the kind of image duplication described in (3) to include overwriting sections of an
325 image, or rotating, stretching or otherwise manipulating an image to hide the fact it is a
326 duplication.

327 Comments that did not belong in any of the categories 1-11 were coded as Other (12).

328 Author response

329 A code was added to indicate whether the author responded on PubPeer to a comment.

330 Journal action

331 This was coded as none, corrected, expression of concern (EOC), or retraction.

332 Cross-check against other sources

333 Where the same author names recurred across multiple comments, a web search was
334 conducted to discover whether there had been significant PubPeer comments
335 associated with their name in other years, and whether a web search yielded further
336 information.

337 3.3. Analysis plan

338 The analysis is descriptive, and no inferential statistics are used. Data from the Annual
339 statements were tabulated in a format similar to that used by Chiarelli et al. (2023) for
340 their analysis of earlier years. The Chiarelli et al. data for 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 are

341 displayed alongside the current analysis of most recent reports. The Chiarelli et al.
 342 data for 2021-2022 are excluded because the authors reported that there was a
 343 relatively small number of reports because several institutions were in the process of
 344 completing their statement at the time of their data collection. In contrast to Chiarelli
 345 et al, the current analysis included tabulation of allegations involving fabrication and
 346 falsification, indicating which institutions had such cases and how the allegations had
 347 been handled.
 348 For PubPeer comments, descriptive data for different categories of comment are
 349 shown, with a more in-depth analysis of institutions with two or more instances of any
 350 category suggestive of research misconduct.

351 4. Results

352 4.1. Quantitative data from annual statements

353 Table 2 shows the numbers of institutions providing an annual statement; data from
 354 earlier years from Chiarelli et al. (2023) are provided for comparison. Data from 2021-
 355 2022 from Chiarelli et al. are excluded. Note that the current analysis takes data from
 356 the latest available statement, which in 32 cases was from 2022-2023 and in 95 cases
 357 was from 2023-2024. The data are coded in the same way as in the report by Chiarelli et
 358 al. (2023), using the categories from the reporting template shown in Table 1.
 359

360 *Table 2: Numbers of allegations in annual statements compared with prior years*

Statistic	2019-2020*	2020-2021*	2022-2023 or 2023-2024**
N institutions in scope	134	134	141
N (%) providing an annual statement	97 (72%)	104 (78%)	127 (90%)
N providing useable quantitative data***			117
Statements reporting at least one misconduct allegation (% of those with useable data)	60 (62%)	60 (58%)	63 (54%)
Statements reporting at least one misconduct investigation (% of those with useable data)	50 (52%)	53 (51%)	46 (39%)
Statements reporting at least one allegation upheld in full (% of those with useable data)	22 (23%)	23 (22%)	27 (23%)
Statements reporting at least one allegation upheld in part (% of those with useable data)	9 (9%)	6 (6%)	12 (10%)

361 *Data from table on p 13, Chiarelli et al. (2023).

362 **Analysis based on most recent annual statement: 56 were from 2023 and 85 from 2024.

363 *** Chiarelli et al. stated that 98% of statements in their corpus provided data on misconduct
 364 allegations, investigations and outcomes
 365

366 As anticipated, institutions that did not produce a statement tended to be smaller and
367 less research-intensive than those that did: for the 14 institutions producing no
368 statement, the 25%, 50% and 75% quantiles for size (HESA, N students) were 7190,
369 13790 and 19230, and for the 127 institutions with a statement the corresponding
370 figures were 10905, 18605 and 25300. Similarly, for the total N publications indexed in
371 Dimensions from 2023-2024, the 25%, 50% and 75% quantiles for those with no
372 statement were 0, 596 and 1776, whereas the corresponding quantiles for those with a
373 statement were 644, 1836 and 4593. All 26 institutions with 6000 or more publications
374 in 2023-2024 produced a statement.

375

376 In many respects, the data from the current analysis are similar to those from previous
377 years, with 54% of institutions reporting one or more allegations of research
378 misconduct, and the remaining 46% reporting no cases. The percentage of allegations
379 that proceeded to formal investigation appears to have declined somewhat from 2019-
380 2021, but the outcomes of investigations were similar: 23% of institutions had at least
381 one allegation that was upheld in full and 10% of institutions had at least one allegation
382 that was upheld in part. Overall, in one year, just over half of all institutions received
383 allegations of research misconduct, and around two thirds of allegations were not
384 upheld.

385

386 For the current analysis some statements could not be included in computations of
387 numbers of allegations etc., because they either omitted key information or appeared
388 to misinterpret the instructions for numeric data. There was also evidence of different
389 interpretations of what needed to be included in the table, and it was sometimes
390 unclear how to interpret the distinction between an allegation that was not acted on
391 and one that proceeded to investigation. A few institutions included cases of
392 misconduct by undergraduates, whereas most treated these under the separate
393 category of "academic misconduct". Available data were interpreted taking into
394 account any accompanying text, but the quantitative data need to be interpreted
395 cautiously, given the uncertainties in the underlying reports. Explanatory notes are
396 provided in the underlying data table to show transparently what interpretive decisions
397 were made (see *Supplement 2*).

398 There were 96 institutions with data both on number of publications in the Dimensions
399 database, and with number of allegations. To get a rough estimate of the proportion of
400 publications associated with an allegation in one year, the total number of allegations
401 for this subset of institutions (227), was divided by the total number of publications in
402 2024 (271420). Thus, the proportion of allegations per publication was 0.00084, or less
403 than one allegation per thousand publications. Not all allegations concern published
404 papers, and so this is if anything an overestimate. As discussed below, this figure
405 should not, however, lead to complacency, given that it contrasts strikingly with
406 estimates of falsification and fabrication from surveys summarised above, which
407 suggest that as many as 14% researchers may produce fraudulent work.

408 Interpretation of number of allegations has to take into account the amount of research
409 activity at an institution: if rates of misconduct were constant across institutions,
410 institutions with more publications would have a greater likelihood that a problem will

411 be found in a publication, just by chance. And indeed, for those that had no allegations,
 412 the 25%, 50% and 75% quantiles for N publications 2023-2024 were 0, 968 and 2000,
 413 whereas for those with allegations, the corresponding figures were 1680, 3257 and
 414 10944, This does not mean, of course, that number of allegations is solely a function of
 415 research activity, but rather it emphasizes that one needs to adjust for size when
 416 comparing institutions.

417 Table 3 turns the focus from the number of institutions with allegations to the raw
 418 numbers of misconduct allegations summed across institutions. The Table shows
 419 numbers that proceeded to formal investigation and/or which were ultimately upheld.

420 *Table 3: Fate of misconduct allegations*

Variable	2019-2020*	2020-2021*	2022-2023 or 2023-2024
N allegations (totalled across institutions)	283	277	238
N proceeding to formal investigation (% of allegations)	183 (65%)	154 (56%)	95 (40%)
N where allegation upheld in part or full (% of investigations)	58 (32%)	95 (61%)	56 (59%)

421 *From Chiarelli et al. (2023) Table on p. 14.

422 Compared to the previous years considered by Chiarelli et al. (2023) the number of
 423 allegations in the statements analysed for 2022-2023/2023-2024 is lower, and when an
 424 investigation is made it is less likely to proceed to formal investigation. One should
 425 beware of interpreting this as a secular trend: a comparison of data from 2021-2022, as
 426 well as disaggregated data for 2022-2023 and 2023-2024 are needed to detect any
 427 temporal pattern.

428 In the current dataset, 60% of misconduct allegations that proceeded to a full
 429 investigation, were upheld - a figure comparable to that for 2020-2021. These numbers
 430 are based on aggregating small numbers across many universities with a very diverse
 431 range of types of misconduct allegation, ranging from authorship dispute to fabrication
 432 and falsification of data. As noted by Chiarelli et al (2023), another factor making it
 433 difficult to interpret results is inclusion of the same case in more than one report if an
 434 investigation takes over a year, or if more than one institution is involved. Nevertheless,
 435 we can conclude that most allegations of research misconduct are resolved informally
 436 without going to formal investigation. In the 2022-2023/2023-2024 data, only around
 437 one in four allegations was ultimately both investigated and upheld.

438 Some allegations can readily be judged on the basis of documentary evidence, such as
 439 ethics approval documents, or duplication of content across documents that confirms
 440 plagiarism; others require judgement of adherence to rules such as authorship
 441 guidelines. Allegations of fabrication or falsification of data typically can be evaluated
 442 using evidence from published articles, but may be difficult to judge for those without
 443 subject-specific expertise.

444 Table 4 shows the overall distribution of categories of misconduct found in allegations,
 445 again aggregated across UK institutions. Data are from the latest report (2022-2023 or
 446 2023-2024), for the subset of statements that coded the type of misconduct.

447

448 *Table 4. Categories of misconduct in most recent annual statements*

Variable	Total allegations	N institutions reporting at least one case
N allegations that could be categorised (totalled across institutions)	238	
Plagiarism	77	32
Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations	74	34
Fabrication or falsification	25	13
Other (including multiple types)	53	29

449 This distribution of categories of misconduct is broadly similar to that reported by
 450 Chiarelli et al. (2023), who found across all in-scope years there were 101 reports giving
 451 a breakdown of categories. These included 203 allegations of plagiarism, 90 cases of
 452 failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations, and 63 cases of
 453 misrepresentation. The categories of fabrication and falsification were not mentioned,
 454 presumably because they were so uncommon.

455 For the current dataset, we took a more detailed look at the fate of cases of fabrication
 456 and falsification, because this type of misconduct is among the most serious.

457 *Table 5. Details of cases of fabrication/falsification*

Institution	N cases	N upheld	notes
University College London, 2023-2024	4	0	No further details except some "closed off at the initial assessment stage" and others "closed off at the screening stage"
University of Oxford, 2023-2024	3	0	All dismissed after preliminary review - no evidence of misconduct
Imperial College, 2023-2024	1	0	(2 further cases listed as ongoing; not considered in this analysis) No further information provided
University of Manchester, 2023-2024	1	1	One case partially upheld
University of Nottingham, 2023-2024	1	1	One PGR student was investigated for academic misconduct, with an allegation upheld. This involved fabrication of reference and false authorship in use of AI software

University of Sheffield, 2023-2024	1	0	No formal investigation
University of Southampton, 2023-2024	1	0	No formal investigation
Queen Mary University of London, 2023-2024	5	0	Each case described here with QMUL case number (8-12) from Annual statement. 8-9: Two separate formal complaints from the same individual were judged to have insufficient evidence of misconduct; also one complaint was "comprised entirely of links to comments posted on PubPeer, ... this did not amount to an actionable complaint." 10: Allegation of fabrication and uncorrected errors in figures. This case had previously been considered and actions had been recommended, but the journal had not acted. 11. Former PhD student alleged falsification in a published journal article. Expert opinion found errors in some of the statistical equations presented, but not sufficient to alter the fundamental conclusions of the paper. 12. Complaint of citation manipulation did not provide substantiation beyond including links to posts on PubPeer - not provided sufficient evidence for a formal investigation.
Cardiff University	2	0	(Case 13 is not concluded so omitted here). 1. A Journal noted comments relating to image manipulation on Pubpeer. This had not been raised as an allegation of ARM with the University, but Head of School carried out a proactive review of the Pubpeer comments. Since the paper involved collaboration between Cardiff and another university, the corresponding author was tasked with reviewing and responding to the specific issues raised on PubPeer with oversight from the relevant university partners. 2. Allegation of image manipulation was concluded after screening panel accepted respondent's statement that this was genuine error, and not intentional and did not significantly impact the overall findings of the paper.

Lancaster University, 2023-2024	1	0	No details
Swansea University, 2023-2024	1	0	No details
De Montfort University, 2022-2023	1	1	A research student admitted to the fabrication of results and the Academic Offense Panel imposed a penalty.
Middlesex University, 2023-2024	2	0	No details

458 Overall, 3 of 25 allegations of fabrication or falsification were upheld. Two of these
459 involved postgraduate students; no information is provided about the other one.

460 4.2. PubPeer comments for 2023

461 Table 6 shows the numbers of PubPeer comments for each type of classification across
462 all UK universities.

463 *Table 6: PubPeer comments classification, by N comments and N universities*

Categories of comments	Total N papers with comments	N papers with comments where main author based at UK university	N UK universities with 2 or more papers in this category (only those where main author at that university)
1.Minor	20	11	1
2.Critique	65	41	6
3.Data_error	44	30	7
4.Data_error_questionable	44	24	6
5.Protocol_error	3	3	0
6.Ethics_breach	5	2	0
7.COI	6	1	0
8.Authorship	3	1	0
9.Plagiarism	9	4	0
10.Papermill	62	27	3
11.Fabrication_falsification	74	49	9
12.Other	13	6	1

464 Table 6 illustrates one problem of using individual publications as evidence for a
465 misconduct allegation: many articles involve collaboration across institutions, which
466 can make it difficult to determine responsibility for conducting an investigation. The
467 column with Total N papers with comments covers many publications where the
468 principal author was outside the UK. The focus of the current analysis is on the next
469 column, showing articles where the first or last author is at a UK institution. Some of the
470 categories that were relatively common in annual statements barely feature in Table 6;
471 PubPeer comments rarely involved protocol errors, ethics breaches, conflicts of
472 interest, authorship disputes, and plagiarism. Furthermore, as shown in the last
473 column, they are not evenly distributed across institutions: note, for instance, that only

474 three institutions had two or more comments suggestive of papermill activity and only
 475 nine institutions had two or more comments suggestive of fabrication or falsification.

476 In this analysis of PubPeer comments for 2023, there were two cases when a research
 477 integrity officer - from the University of Dundee - responded to a critique of work on
 478 PubPeer (<https://pubpeer.com/publications/36FD011475B9977649B1868A5E9BD9>;
 479 <https://pubpeer.com/publications/72FBFBA261EA1B463B204D44173F01>). Apart from
 480 this isolated instance, however, there was no indication that institutions engaged with
 481 PubPeer as a means of monitoring research outputs.

482 Table 7 looks in more detail at PubPeer comments that were in categories that
 483 suggested research misconduct. The Table includes only the 14 universities where
 484 there were two or more papers with a comment in a given category. Data are shown
 485 using a more lax criterion, where any university with a comment coded as 4-11, in
 486 *Supplement 4*. There were 42 universities meeting that criterion.

487 The clustering of comments in Table 7 that characterises this table is not accidental. As
 488 noted above, a sleuth who finds evidence of falsification or fabrication of data will be
 489 motivated to check other work by the author(s) for confirmatory evidence. A single
 490 article with a manipulated image is unlikely to be taken as sufficient grounds for a
 491 research integrity investigation, especially given that most publications have multiple
 492 authors. Unless there is an author credit statement, it may be unclear who was
 493 responsible for the manipulation. Scrutiny of a wider range of outputs by the same
 494 authors will usually provide an indication of whether there is a persistent pattern of
 495 fabrication/falsification, and which authors are associated with it.

496 *Table 7: Characteristics of comments that implied misconduct, grouped by institution*

Institution	Category	N	Notes
University of Bristol	Data error questionable	2	(1-2) All relate to one research group: This case featured in For Better Science .
University of Bristol	Fabrication falsification	10	(1-10) Two articles have Expression of Concern. All ten relate to one group, which had featured in For Better Science .
University of Cambridge	Fabrication falsification	2	(1) PI has 2 previous PubPeer comments re image splicing; (2) EOC for this paper; Author has no other PubPeer
Cardiff University	Data error questionable	3	(1-3) All cases where there was no response to queries re figure duplications. These all relate to one research centre that was featured on For Better Science in 2018 : and again in 2023 .
Cardiff University	Fabrication falsification	2	(1) This comment relates to same centre as previous row.

			(2) All authors from Pakistan except last (senior) author from Cardiff Pharmacy. He has PubPeer comments on other papers reporting image issues.
University of Durham	Papermill	2	(1) Out-of-scope article in special issue; author has dual affiliation Durham Business School and Chinese university; no other obvious PubPeer (though name disambiguation difficult); Google search on this name with "Durham" yields no hits, suggesting this may have been a student who has now left. (2) Retracted article from tanu.pro paper mill; whole special issue retracted
Imperial College	Data error questionable	2	(1-2) Both comments relate to articles by the same Professor in collaborative articles with China; he has other papers commented on in PubPeer and is mentioned in For Better Science .
Kings College London	Data error questionable	3	(1) Has correction with remarkable number of figure changes; Senior author has co-authored some other papers with PubPeer queries re data/figures but not as corresponding author. (2) Senior author co-authored one other paper years ago with queries that were resolved. (3) 1st author was at KCL, now Japan; last author is Prof at KCL with other PubPeer comments on articles with image queries.
University of Leeds	Fabrication falsification	2	(1) Retracted for unresolved figure irregularities; Neither 1st nor last author has any other PubPeer comments; (2) Journal correction for figure anomalies, though these involve more than duplication; Last author has no other PubPeer comments
University of Leicester	Fabrication falsification	2	(1) Senior author has other PubPeer comments for image manipulation and COI; also featured in For Better Science . (2) Senior author has co-authored other papers with PubPeer image concerns, but not as corresponding author.

University of Lincoln	Fabrication falsification	2	(1) Last author Professor of Nanoscience from Lincoln; some engagement on PubPeer but not convincing; article retracted; He is featured in For Better Science . (2) Last author Associate Professor of Pharmacology and Therapeutics; features in For Better Science .
University of Manchester	Fabrication falsification	3	(1-2) Same corresponding author: Senior Lecturer; although author engaged on PubPeer did not convincingly address issues; (3) last author dual appointment with Manchester Biomedical Research Centre. Features in For Better Science .
University of Portsmouth	Papermill	2	(1) Retracted. Last author joint affiliation with Portsmouth and Saudi Arabia; (2) Retracted; last author Emeritus Professor of Pharmacognosy
Queen Mary University of London	Data error questionable	3	(1-3) All with same senior author, featured in For Better Science .
Queen Mary University of London	Fabrication falsification	15	(1-8) All with same senior author as for previous row. Two retracted, one EOC. Featured here: For Better Science . (9-14) One journal correction. Author featured in For Better Science . (15) authors from Argentina except for last author, Emeritus Professor of Biochemistry, now deceased.
University of Salford	Papermill	4	(1-4) All co-authored by Professor of Fluid Mechanics, Propulsion and Nanomechanics Research
University College London	Data error questionable	2	(1) Last author Director of The KCL Centre for Cell and Gene Therapy; featured in For Better Science regarding another article (2) last author is Associate Professor; has one prior PubPeer comment where he engaged positively

University College London	Fabrication falsification	3	(1) Last (corresponding) author has honorary position at Cancer Institute. He has coauthored several articles flagged on PubPeer for image manipulation; (2-3) First author was research fellow at UCL, now at Swansea. He has co-authored one other paper noted on PubPeer for image manipulation concerns.
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498 The clusters of comments seen for Bristol, Cardiff and Queen Mary University of
499 London (QMUL) appear to provide strong enough evidence for an allegation of research
500 misconduct to be taken seriously, particularly when one bears in mind that this table is
501 confined to PubPeer comments from 2023, so additional comments may be found by
502 searching other years. Nevertheless, it seems that in none of these cases was a case
503 upheld. Nearly all the comments for QMUL related to one of two research groups. In
504 the annual statement, the QMUL research integrity officer noted two allegations that
505 were judged to have insufficient evidence of misconduct; one complaint was
506 *"comprised entirely of links to comments posted on PubPeer, ... this did not amount to*
507 *an actionable complaint."*

508 5. Discussion

509 The quantitative analysis of the most recent annual statements by UK universities
510 obtained results broadly similar to those reported by Chiarelli et al (2023) for previous
511 years. In brief:

- 512 • Allegations of research misconduct were rare, particularly in smaller universities
513 with a primary focus on teaching. Across the whole set of universities, there was
514 less than one allegation per thousand publications.
- 515 • The most common types of research misconduct that featured in annual
516 statements were plagiarism and failure to meet legal, ethical and professional
517 obligations. There are insufficient data to be certain, but the impression is that
518 these types of misconduct mostly affected graduate students rather than
519 academic staff.
- 520 • Research fraud other than plagiarism, i.e. fabrication/falsification of data, was
521 rarely reported: there were 25 cases from 13 universities, only three of which
522 were upheld.

523 This analysis was complemented by an analysis of comments on publications on the
524 post-publication peer review website PubPeer. The focus here is on comments relating
525 to articles where the main author(s) are from a UK institution.

- 526 • As shown in Table 6, the number of publications from UK institutions attracting
527 comments is relatively small. Even if every PubPeer comment were

528 investigated, there seems no danger of UK Research Integrity Officers spending
529 "every waking hour reviewing PubPeer comments" (Caron, Lye, Bierer, & Barnes,
530 2024, p. 16).

- 531 • Around 20% of comments concerned discussion of aspects of methods, logic or
532 results that appeared to correspond to regular academic debate. A further 20%
533 were either minor comments, or were consistent with "honest error", where the
534 author engages with explanation or correction.
- 535 • Other comments reported more serious issues that appeared indicative of
536 research misconduct: 14% of comments related to publications that seemed to
537 be associated with paper mills; 25% of comments provided evidence of data
538 fabrication/falsification, and a further 12% reported serious errors in articles
539 that were not adequately addressed by authors. Only 2% of comments related
540 to plagiarism.
- 541 • There were 14 universities with two or more comments that suggested serious
542 research misconduct, and in four cases there were several such comments
543 focused on specific research groups. Although these cases had received critical
544 commentary on blogs, and some of the publications had had expressions of
545 concern, no cases of research misconduct relating to these had been upheld by
546 institutions.

547 Taken together, both annual statements and PubPeer reports found a low frequency of
548 reports of problems. This might seem reassuring, were it not for the discrepancy with
549 estimates of research misconduct from surveys, which imply that many cases of
550 research misconduct go undetected or unreported.

551 It is also clear that allegations of fabrication and falsification are an uncommon reason
552 for institutional research misconduct investigations, which focus predominantly on
553 plagiarism, authorship disputes and breach of professional standards, including ethics
554 approvals.

555 The greatest concern to emerge from this analysis is that in the rare cases where
556 serious allegations of fabrication/falsification were considered, they were typically
557 dismissed by institutions. Of course, it cannot be assumed that all such allegations are
558 well-founded, but the evidence from PubPeer is typically unarguable in cases where
559 one can see that published images have been manipulated. While there may be debate
560 about who is responsible for the manipulation, repeated comments regarding data
561 fabrication/falsification in different publications from the same research group should
562 be taken seriously.

563 6. Conclusions and recommendations

564 I started by considering the mismatch in views of research integrity investigations by
565 research integrity officers and sleuths that was apparent in the FAIRS survey by Bishop
566 (2025). The current analyses show that, consistent with the view of research integrity
567 officers, the numbers of allegations of serious research misconduct in UK universities
568 are low. However, the mismatch between numbers of allegations and survey data on

569 rates of fraudulent research practices suggest that much problematic research goes
570 undetected or unreported.

571 Although some institutions are still reporting in an ad hoc fashion, it appears that the
572 Concordat to Support Research Integrity has helped UK institutions to follow common
573 standards (cf. the situation in the USA: Gunsalus, Marcus, & Oransky, 2018). Any
574 country that does have a system of institutional self-regulation needs a body that
575 ensures consistent standards of reporting and processing of allegations. Most
576 institutions had their annual statements available on the institutional website, but
577 these were not always easy to find. A centralised approach to reporting, with
578 requirement for a standard format for quantitative data, would be welcome.

579 A concerning observation was that, consistent with the views of sleuths, when serious
580 cases of research fraud occurred, they seldom led to the institution concluding that
581 there was research misconduct, even where there is strong evidence of fabrication or
582 falsification in more than one publication.

583 One point to emerge from the analysis of annual statements is that many research
584 integrity officers have no experience with data falsification or fabrication and may lack
585 confidence in determining what might be plausible honest error. It is not uncommon for
586 a PubPeer commentator to briefly indicate areas of figures with overlap using coloured
587 rectangles. A naive reader may not recognise when this is indicative of digital
588 manipulation and hence fail to appreciate it is evidence of fabrication/falsification of
589 data (Rossner & Yamada, 2004). Those making allegations need to spell out the issues
590 that have been identified at a level of detail that can be understood by a non-expert, so
591 that a defence of "honest error" is not accepted when it is not plausible.

592 A particular issue frequently alluded to in the FAIRS survey (Bishop, 2025) as well as in
593 allegations on the *For Better Science* website, is institutional conflict of interest. Some
594 allegations of research fraud involve senior figures who hold important institutional
595 positions and bring in large amounts of grant income. While it may be reasonable for
596 institutions to investigate matters such as authorship disputes or plagiarism in
597 postgraduate theses, it is questionable whether they can realistically be expected to be
598 objective when investigating allegations against their own senior researchers.
599 Currently, guidance from the UK Research Integrity Office notes that if a case
600 progresses to the full investigation stage, then at least one member of the panel must
601 be from outside the organisation (Parry & Sainsbury, 2023), but the process is still run
602 by the institution that employs the researcher under investigation.

603 In a wide-ranging review of research fraud, Freckleton (2016) documented numerous
604 cases that were inadequately investigated; as noted by Redman (2023), the inherent
605 conflict of an institution investigating itself and its faculty is "*a flaw that should require*
606 *independent outside review*" (p 115-6). One way to take pressure off research integrity
607 officers and give greater confidence in the process if allegations of fraud in the form of
608 falsification and fabrication of data were handled by a body independent of the
609 institution, as proposed by Freckleton (2016). In a review of international practices, the
610 Australian National Health and Medical Research Council noted that some countries

611 have created such bodies for exactly this situation, and it will be of interest to study
612 how feasible and effective they are, and to note any unintended consequences. For
613 instance, a regulatory body run by government could create new conflicts if political
614 considerations affect decision-making. On the other hand, an independent body might
615 be more efficient as well as avoiding conflict of interest, because it would employ
616 people with expertise in handling cases of research misconduct. One point to emerge
617 from the current analysis is that the typical research integrity officer in a UK university
618 has no experience of handling a case of falsification or fabrication of data.

619 A third issue concerns whether institutional research integrity officers should be more
620 proactive in tackling research integrity matters, or continue to adopt an exclusively
621 responsive mode where an investigation is initiated only when an allegation is received
622 in an appropriate format. Although PubPeer is far from comprehensive in its coverage,
623 it could help institutions get ahead of integrity issues if they were able to scan PubPeer
624 for comments affecting their researchers and encourage authors to resolve these if
625 possible. However, this would require a level of expertise in evaluating PubPeer
626 comments, which are not always straightforward to evaluate.

627 A final point concerns transparency of research integrity investigations. The prior
628 UKCORI report (Chiarelli et al., 2023) stated that quantitative data were omitted to
629 "*avoid metricisation*", and identity of institutions was masked to avoid "*incorrect or*
630 *inappropriate generalisations that may not reflect the diversity of institutions*
631 *considered*". However, the wide variety in allegations of research misconduct and
632 responses to them is one reason why it can be useful to look at institutions in more
633 granular detail. The aggregate figures alone are not informative for guiding future
634 behaviour. Here the analysis documented individual cases, which may help one
635 identify where there is good practice and where there are problems.

636 Oransky and Marcus (2025) took a step further and made a cogent case that reports of
637 misconduct investigations should be made public, as has been done in the past by the
638 US Office of Research Integrity. Currently, investigations referred to in annual
639 statements by UK universities are anonymised. A common concern about transparent
640 reporting of results of investigations is that it may stigmatise members of a research
641 group who were not involved in misconduct, and it was noteworthy that in a recent
642 survey of attitudes to sanctions (Bishop, 2025), there was widespread agreement with
643 the statement: "It is important to be aware of and mitigate collateral damage that may
644 be caused to other members of a research group if one member is found to have
645 committed serious research misconduct." On the other hand, without transparent
646 reporting, where an allegation of misconduct is upheld, it is easy for the researcher in
647 question to relocate and continue fraudulent activities elsewhere, with damaging
648 consequences for a new set of collaborators. For instance, Retraction Watch (2025)
649 reported that an investigation by the University of Manchester had confirmed that one
650 of their former students had been running a paper mill, but it is evident that the student
651 went on to another university and it is unclear whether this case was included in their
652 annual statement for 2023-4. It is at least as important to be fully transparent when an
653 investigation concludes there is no misconduct: if the process is shrouded in secrecy,
654 then this creates suspicion of a cover-up, which does not do any favours to the

655 researchers accused of misconduct. This is illustrated in a case from Queen Mary
656 University where statements of "no misconduct" about one researcher have been
657 publicly challenged (Sinha, 2023).

658 Virtually every UK university has a section on their website that echoes sentiments
659 similar to those stated here by UCL "*All staff and students at UCL are expected to*
660 *promote and maintain a culture of honesty, openness and responsibility, enabling all*
661 *research to be conducted with integrity. Ensuring the highest standards of integrity in all*
662 *aspects of our research activities allows others to have trust and confidence in the*
663 *methods used and the findings.*" Greater transparency in reporting of investigations
664 could help garner such trust and confidence.

665

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761 The author reports no conflict of interests.

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763 Supplementary material

764 Supplementary data files together with R code for analysis have been deposited on
765 Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/15373147>.

766 **Supplement 1.** Zip file with pdf version of Annual Statements on Research Integrity by
767 UK Institutions

768 **Supplement 2.** Annual statements coded spreadsheet (AnnStatementsCoded.csv)
769 with data dictionary (Supp2_data_dictionary_ann_statements.csv).

770 **Supplement 3.** Spreadsheet of coded PubPeer data (Supplement
771 3_codedPubPeer.csv) with data dictionary (Supp3_data_dictionary.csv)

772 **Supplement 4.** Selected PubPeer cases for Table 7 (Supplement 4_selectedcases.csv)

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